

Conference Abstract

Detection and Characterization of Active Microbial Cells in Salt Cavern Brine

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Abstract

Salt caverns have been used for decades as natural gas storage facilities and are now target of large-scale underground H₂ storage to secure national energy transition goals. Contrary to CH₄, H₂ is a universal electron donor for microbial anaerobic respiration. Suitable electron acceptors are sulfate and carbonate, which dissolve from gypsum, anhydrite and lime that can make up 10 % of subsurface salt formations. Whilst sulfate reduction is inherently linked to the formation of H₂S, microbial CO₂ reduction can generate acetate, which can be used as carbon source by diverse microorganisms. Thus, supporting other microbial side effects, such as H₂S formation, clogging and H₂ consumption. However, microbial diversity and activity in salt caverns are selectively controlled by salt concentrations close to saturation and limited availability of organic carbon. If these conditions allow for microbial activity was investigated in our study.

To circumvent long enrichment times associated with high salinity and limited nutrient availability, we used a stable isotope labelling approach combined with nano-scale secondary ion mass spectrometry analysis (SIP-nanoSIMS) to investigate H₂-dependant microbial activity in two brine samples and compared them with that of an extremely halophilic enrichment culture (MP-32). Heavy carbonate and water (¹³CO₂ and ²H₂O) served as tracers for microbial activity. Microbial H₂ consumption was additionally investigated in microcosm experiments with brine and rock salt over a period of 200 days. Setups with MP-32 served as a positive control. Subsequently, MP-32 was selected for

metagenome sequencing to explore potential metabolic pathways and strategies for osmoadaptation.

Analysis of the microbial community composition in brine revealed that members of the Desulfohalobiaceae, Halobacteria and Halanaerobiales were present in all caverns and their relative abundance increased during incubation with H₂ as electron donor although sulfate reduction was not observed. But incubation with H₂ resulted in an increased uptake of ¹³C from ¹³CO₂ in 1.6 to 3.6 % of the cells compared to incubations without H₂. Uptake of ²H from ²H₂O was detected in 20 to 30 % of the cells and was higher when H₂ was not offered as an electron donor. Similar results were obtained from the enrichment culture MP-32, which was grown in medium with reduced salinity compared to the salt cavern brine. Uptake of ¹³C was 10-fold higher when incubated with H₂ and nearly all cells incorporated ²H with and without H₂. A total of eight metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) with a completion of more than 90 % could be recovered from MP-32. Two of them belonged to Desulfohalobiaceae and can be characterized as autotrophic sulfate reducers by means of the Acetyl-Coenzyme A pathway that compensates osmotic stress by synthesizing small organic molecules. Collectively, our findings provide a new approach to study microbial activity that is strongly impacted by high salinity and an improved understanding of their genomic potential.

Keywords

salt cavern, halophile, SRB, underground gas storage, nanoSIMS, anaerobe

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Conflicts of interest

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